

Social problems of staff turnover within organisations and the ways of address these issues

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Abstract

The article examines the dissatisfaction with personnel in the organization, their classification, the impact of dissatisfaction with the personnel of enterprises and organizations on the efficiency of work, ways to overcome them and the theory of foreign experience in this area.

Keywords: Staff dissatisfaction, dissatisfaction, social problems, economic problems, motivation, organization and staff,

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Introduction

Personnel dissatisfaction is associated with the employee's dissatisfaction with the workplace or the organization's dissatisfaction with the behavior of a particular specialist employee. This indicator is also called the "index of the revolving door" and it shows how long the technician has worked.

The main types of staff turnover are: Will be internal, external, physical, hidden, natural.

1. Intra-organizational - associated with labor movements within the organization.
2. Outer- between organizations and sectors of the economy.
3. Physical-dissatisfaction with personnel includes employees leaving the organization for various reasons.
4. Latent (psychological) - staff dissatisfaction arises among employees who do not leave the company from the outside, but actually leave it, excluded from organizational activities.
5. Natural - (3-5% per year) contributes to the timely renewal of the team and does not require special measures from the management and the personnel department¹.

Today we can see negative factors that lead to staff turnover in all organizations, such factors do not affect the further development of the organization's activities, and to prevent staff turnover, each organization must have its own strategy. Today, we see that in organizations, employees often change jobs, in which case a new employee joins the organization, adapts to the work of an old employee and continues to work effectively, the organization suffers in all respects due to the cost of training and inefficient use of time.

Several factors can be listed that lead to employee turnover in organizations. For example, over the years of independence, there has been an urgent need for staff in many areas, and the recruitment process has not paid sufficient attention to the specialization of candidates, which has led to a lack of knowledge and capacity of staff. Today we also see that many areas are lagging behind in development and improvement, although trained personnel specialization is a different direction, but in general they work in a different direction.

In order for any organization to fully and effectively achieve its goals, it must first of all be connected with the organization's personnel. Staff turnover affects the efficiency of organizations, and this is a big problem for some companies and organizations. Organizations think that their biggest problem with staff turnover is the constant recruitment and training to improve their skills, organizations can hire and select employees in the most effective ways, they can also improve their professional skills. Dismissal can be caused by material, non-material and social problems in the organization. Dissatisfaction of employees in the organization can put undue pressure on the team, first of all, the organization spends additional money and time; it also brings stress, fatigue and a sense of irresponsibility to existing employees due to overwork. Foreign experience shows that as a result of staff dissatisfaction, the average is about 30 thousand pounds (about 45 thousand US dollars). These metrics include logistics costs, ad agency payments, time spent by management interviewing candidates and time spent with staff, and new hires' salaries for the time they spent in organizations and businesses. There is a surplus of staff in the organization, especially among young people, and they do the same among their peers, while the constant discontent of the staff can complicate the life of other employees and, as a result, reduce the quality of products².

¹ Job Dissatisfaction: Meaning, Causes, Reasons and Effects

² Employee Turnover Rates: An Industry Comparison

To effectively deal with employee dissatisfaction, it is necessary to constantly monitor its coefficient and study the situation in the organization. In the modern market, there are automated personnel accounting systems, which include modules for personnel planning, the effectiveness of the personnel service and monitoring the status of employees in the organization. One of the information systems for personnel management with the necessary functionality is the "1C: Payroll and Human Resources 8" system, which contains the "Personnel Exchange Rate" report, which allows to track the current level of employee dissatisfaction both throughout the organization and in general. Knowing the reason for the layoffs of employees, it is necessary to take measures to eliminate the problem. For example, if the wage rate is to blame, it is necessary to determine whether there is a financial opportunity to increase wages, the size of bonuses, or introduce other options for material incentives for employees. If some of the personnel are dissatisfied with the working conditions, it is necessary to make a decision on the possibility of improving them.

The human factor in the work environment can negatively affect the rapid change in the performance of young employees in organizations, for example, young employees may suffer from old stereotypes, dislike of innovation, inability to see.

Freedom and materialism prevail among the key factors that attract many young people from government agencies to private sector organizations. They need to create conditions no less than private enterprises to work in public organizations. Factors associated with old-fashioned views, including other subjective ones, should not be negatively influenced.

We can group the problems of staff turnover in the activities of local public administration authorities as follows:

- economic problems (the level of wages, prices and tariffs for communal and consumer goods, employment);
- social problems (housing and its quality, the work of medical institutions, family conflicts);
- Problems of social infrastructure (quality of housing and communal services, ecology, transport)
- Ensuring the rule of law (human rights, corruption, bribery and extortion, etc.).

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "In many organizations and departments, instead of implementing the most important programs of social and economic development, in most cases there are only meetings and ill-considered decisions, practical work and paperwork."³

In order to prevent staff turnover in the organization, first of all, both parties must fully comply with their wishes.

What does the organization expect from the employee?

- Discipline
- High performance
- High efficiency
- Initiative
- Loyalty
- Participation in the activities of the organization
- Incentives from work
- Willingness to work on yourself, improve your knowledge and skills

³ <https://kun.uz/news/2017/08/10/mirzieev-mazlisbozlik-va-kogozbozlikni-keskin-kamajtirisni-buordi>

What does the employee want from the organization?

- Good salary
- Stable workplace
- Interesting job
- Convenient work schedule
- Achieving a specific need
- Respect each other's
- Conditions for the demonstration of abilities
- Comfortable and long stay
- Terms of the initiative
- Responsible work
- Easy job

Relationship problems that lead to employee turnover in the organization

Worker	Commitment renouncement	Organization
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaving work • Trick at work • Dismissal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of loyalty • Insecurity • Mutual dissatisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non – payment of salary • Strict punishment • Strict control • Releasing

In short, to prevent employee turnover in organizations, first of all, it is necessary to manage relations in the organization, behavior and the human resource management system.

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